

Continuity Equation Versus Free Particle Flow/Flux Quantum Equations

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The continuity equation: $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } d(x,t) + \text{grad dot } d(x,t)u(x,t) = 0$ ((1)) where $d(x,t)$ is density and $u(x,t)$ a velocity field appears in the literature as a fundamental equation of “continuity”. For example, it follows from Boltzmann’s transport equation (and conservation of mass) and leads to a wave equation for sound when combined with a pressure equation (1). A continuity type equation also follows from Maxwell’s em equations and includes the Poynting momentum $b \text{ El } \times \text{ B}$ where b is a constant, El electric field and B magnetic field. This equation describes light. Finally the continuity equation is used in a number of derivations of the Schrodinger equation (e.g. (2)).

In previous notes (3) we have argued that two flux/flow equations for free particles: $\frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } A = p$ ((2a)) and $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } A = -E$ ((2b)), with $A = -Et + px$ being a solution, hold for both quantum particles with rest mass and without (e.g. photons/phonons). These equations are also involved with flux which begs the question: What is the relationship between the two?

We investigate this in this note.

Continuity Equation and Classical Waves

Classical waves are subject to:

$E = pv$ ((3)) where v is the constant velocity depending on parameters in the system.

For example, this leads to a constant speed of light in a vacuum or constant velocity of sound at certain temperatures etc. Classical waves follow as a solution of a classical wave equation i.e.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} W = \frac{1}{vv} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W \quad ((4))$$

((4)) may be derived from Newtonian mechanics for a wave on a string. For sound, the continuity equation ((1)) together with a pressure equation may be used to obtain the wave equation (1). Finally separate classical wave equations for the electric field and magnetic field (for a system with no charges or current) may be obtained from Maxwell’s equations.

The point we wish to stress is that one needs the classical wave equation (or a similar equation) to obtain a periodic solution. Periodicity is key. The periodic solution has an argument of $-Et + px$ which is a Lorentz invariant. The relationship ((3)) $E = pv$ is only one type of solution which keeps $-Et + px$ stationary. Another is consistent with particles with rest mass.

With an argument of $-Et + px$ from the wave equation, it may be noted that any function:

$$f(-Et + px) \quad ((5)) \quad \text{with } E = pv \quad \text{and } d(x,t) = f, \quad du = f(x,t) v \quad (v = \text{constant})$$

is a solution of the continuity equation ((1)). Thus the continuity equation by itself is not particularly linked to a periodic wave. Furthermore, given that is linked to $E=pv$, it does not apply to a free particle with rest mass and constant velocity.

Two Solutions to a Stationary $A = -Et + px$

$-Et + px$ appears as an argument in classical waves and is a Lorentz invariant. The energy-momentum relation ((4)) $E=pv$ follows from $dA=0 = -E dt + p dx$. This is not the only solution, however. Performing a Lorentz transformation on $(0, m_0)$, $(0, t)$ for a particles with rest mass m_0 shows that:

Before: $A = -m_0 t$

After: $-m_0/\sqrt{1-vv} * t' + m_0 v/\sqrt{1-vv} * x'$ with $t'=t/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $x'/t'=v$ yields $-m_0 t$

Thus there are two solutions which keep A constant. One is the classical wave with $E=pv$ (v constant) and $p=E(v)/v$ for a particle with rest mass.

The particle with rest mass solution is also associated with $A=-Et+px$. The question is how may one obtain a flow/flux equation which describes such a particle?

Flow/Flux Equations

In previous notes (3) we argued that one may relate energy and momentum flow using two flux/flow equations instead of the continuity equation:

$$d/dx \text{ partial } A = p \quad \text{and} \quad d/dt \text{ partial } A = -E \quad ((2a))((2b))$$

We argued that quantum mechanics for a free particle (relativistic or nonrelativistic) follows from ((2a)) and ((2b)) by creating eigenvalue equations:

$$id/dt \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad \text{and} \quad -d/dx \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((5a)) \quad ((5b))$$

A question immediately arises (which we have not attempted to answer in previous notes). Why should one create an eigenfunction equation in the first place? We try to argue that ((5a))((5b)) take the place of the continuity equation ((1)). For both a quantum particle with rest mass and a classical wave there is energy leaving an x position as well as energy flow. For a particle with rest mass there is no physical wave in a medium (i.e. no string, no gas etc) so probability for a constant velocity particle in space (thinking in terms of flow) stays constant, yet one must describe a loss of energy in time and an energy flow. We argue that ((5a)) and ((5b)) describe this. The first equation shows there is a loss of energy $-E$, but that the probability $\exp(iA)$ stays constant. ((5b)) shows that there is an energy flow, but the probability remains constant. This we argue is the continuity scenario for a quantum particle with rest mass. The consequences are large in that conditional probability of a free particle is complex $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

It may be immediately seen that probability density for a free particle $W^*W=1$ and density times velocity ρ/m satisfy the continuity equation ((1)), but as $0+0=0$. There have been a number of derivations of the Schrodinger equation in the literature (e.g. (2)) which use the continuity equation with density applying to a non-bound state. (The continuity equation does not appear to apply to the bound state because W , the wavefunction is real and d/dt partial $WW=0$, but $\text{grad dot } WW$ ($-idW/dx/W$) ($1/m$) is not zero.) The point we wish to make is that for a free particle described by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, the continuity equation does not seem to yield any information. As a result we focus on the flow/flux equations ((2a))(2b)).

Continuity Equation and Light

As noted above, the continuity equation ((1)) applies to classical waves as any $f(-Et+kx)$ is a solution. $\cos(-Et+kx)$ is a solution for E (electric field) and B (magnetic field) from Maxwell's equations i.e. Maxwell's equations already provide the physics of the solution in terms of E and B . They also contain a frequency E and wavelength proportional to $1/p$. One does not know that these are linked to photon energy and momentum respectively at this point. If one could form a continuity equation ((1)) (as Poynting did), one would have an expression for energy density and momentum density as functions of frequency E and momentum p . Averaging these over a wavelength then shows that the frequency of E and B is indeed the photon energy and the wavelength is proportional to $1/p$. Thus the continuity equation is useful for zero rest mass objects.

The continuity equation is also consistent with the Schrodinger equation for non-bound states (2) as long as one does not have a free particle. For the free particle one has $0+0=0$. As a result, we use the flow/flux equations ((2a)) ((2b)) and think in terms of loss of E and flow of p which are not densities, but the full energy and energy flow to describe the free particle. This approach applies to both quantum free particles with nonzero rest mass and classical wave type objects (phonons/photons), but does not yield energy or momentum densities for such a free particle. The Poynting results for the photon show that there may be complicated "structure" to energy density and momentum, but a full em theory in addition to the continuity equation (1) is needed to show this and such a theory is usually not available for nonzero rest mass particles.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the continuity equation d/dt partial $d(x,t) + \text{grad dot } d(x,t)u(x,t) = 0$ ((1)) appears throughout physics and is considered a key equation in describing changes in density linked to flows. For example it follows from Boltzmann's transport equation (with conservation of mass) and may be used with other equations to create a classical wave equation for sound. It also appears in a somewhat different form (no $d(x,t)u(x,t)$) in Poynting's continuity equation of light (from Maxwell's em equations). Finally, it appears in a number of derivations of the Schrodinger equation (2).

We argue that flow/flux equations d/dx partial $\exp(iA) = p$ and d/dt partial $\exp(iA) = -E$ describe basic energy loss and flow for a free particle and lead to the Lorentz invariant solution $A = -Et + px$. This has two solutions for stationary A . One is the classical wave $E = pv$ ($v = \text{constant}$) and the other $p = E(v)/v$ (the nonzero rest mass solution). One may obtain quantum mechanics for a free

particle with rest mass (relativistic/nonrelativistic) by assuming one wants equations which show the energy loss $-E$ and flow p , but also show probability does not change at the same time i.e. is invariant. This leads to a complex periodic solution $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

We argue that this is the flow in the quantum nonzero rest mass free particle picture. An eigenvalue equation form ((2a))((2b)) yields this picture i.e. $-id/dt \exp(iA)=E\exp(iA)$ and $-id/dx\exp(iA) = p\exp(iA)$. The density which follows from free particle quantum mechanics $W^*W=1$ and flow W^*Wp/m lead to $0+0=0$ in the continuity equation so it is not really useful for a free particle.

The continuity equation ((1)) becomes useful if one has an existing theory for a classical wave like Maxwell's em theory. The flux/flow equations already point to a $\cos(-Et+px)$ solution in the problem, but do not yield energy density of momentum density $E \times B$ expressions. It may also be useful for describing unbound state, non free particle quantum (nonzero rest mass) scenarios

References

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